

A STUDY ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO BANKING SECTOR IN WEST BENGAL

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ABSTRACT:

Banks emphasize on customer satisfaction to survive in the competitive environment of banking sector. Private sector banks provide high quality service to customers with the help of technology. The infrastructure of public sector banks are very poor. Rural masses suffer due to inadequate number of bank branches in rural areas. Urban customers prefer online banking more than rural customers. Rural customers are not properly aware about the banking facilities. The banking habits of urban people is more than rural people. The level of customer satisfaction in private sector banks is more in comparison to public sector banks. Customer satisfaction is very important to increase customer loyalty. Customer satisfaction has immense effect behind customer retention. Both public and private sector banks emphasize on customer satisfaction to enhance customer loyalty. The study is based on primary data and secondary data. Primary data has been collected from public and private sector banks in West Bengal. In this paper, an attempt has been made to find out various aspects of customer satisfaction in public and private sector banks in West Bengal.

KEYWORDS:

BANK, BANKING SERVICES, CUSTOMER, CUSTOMER SATISFACTION.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The competitive environment of banking sector has compelled the banks to emphasize on customer satisfaction. Private sector banks adopt modern technology more than public sector banks. The number of bank branches in urban areas is more than rural areas. The inclination of urban customers towards online banking has increased in recent years. Banks should take appropriate measures to increase banking habits among the rural masses. Customer satisfaction plays significant role to improve customer loyalty. The infrastructure of banks in urban areas is better than rural areas. Rural masses avoid banking services due to lack of awareness. Banks should take proper steps to increase the awareness of rural people regarding banking facilities. Private sector banks emphasize on customer satisfaction more than public sector banks. The infrastructure of private sector banks is better than public sector banks. Urban people are more interested in online banking than rural people. Banks focus on quality of service as it helps to enhance the level of customer satisfaction. Customer satisfaction is essential for customer retention for both private and public sector banks. The objective of the study is to find out various aspects of customer satisfaction in public and private sector banks in West Bengal.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Banks provide banking services to the customers with the help of technology (Zafar et al., 2011). Banks emphasize to

increase the quality of service in order to enhance customer satisfaction (Kampakaki and Papthanasion, 2016). Banks are compelled to focus on customer satisfaction due to increased competition and recent technological developments (Cabanillas et al., 2013). Customer satisfaction depends on timely information, customer relationship management, awareness of customers, web portal management (Sunith, 2019). Banks adopt various strategies to enhance customer satisfaction through e-banking (Sohail and Shanmugham, 2003). Customers avail banking services from homes and offices with the help of e-banking (Panda and Misra, 2017). Mobile banking faces many challenges such as demographic challenges, regulatory challenges and economic challenges (Deshwal, 2015). E-banking has several advantages such as convenience, low cost, mobility (Sahu, 2016). Customer satisfaction depends on psychological and economic factors (Kumbhar, 2011). Banks are emphasizing to increase customer satisfaction level with the view to improve customer loyalty (Suleiman et al., 2012). Banks face difficulties due to poor internet services (Jindal, 2016). E-banking depends on advanced technology to deliver banking services to customers (Balogun et al., 2013). Banks are adopting modern technologies to deliver e-banking services to customers (Ayyash, 2017). Long term relationship with customers plays important role behind the success of banks (Esmaeili et al., 2013). The quality of e-banking services plays vital

role to influence customer satisfaction (Madavan and Vethirajan, 2020). Banking sector plays important role in the economic system (Dhanraj and Saikumar, 2016). Regional rural banks deliver banking services to rural masses (Sharma et al., 2019). Regional rural banks play vital role behind the development of rural areas (Tigari and Gaganadeepa, 2019). Rural masses face difficulties to avail credit facilities (Ahmed, 2020). Rural masses avoid banking services due to the fear of bank charges (Kuddus et al., 2020). Digital banking in rural banking sector requires the involvement of rural people (Das et al., 2017). Rural banks are highly benefited by the restructuring policy of banking sector by the Government of India (Khankhoje and Sathye, 2008). Awareness of customer is very important for the success of banking sector (Puttaswamy, 2018). The nature of banking sector in India is changing fast (Anita et al., 2018). Customer satisfaction plays vital role behind the success or failure of e-banking in private and public sector banks (Prasad et al., 2019). Customers conduct wide range of financial transactions through e-banking (Faisal and Tayachi, 2021). E-banking is better than traditional banking in delivering banking services to customers (Hada, 2020). Customers need not visit bank office to avail e-banking facilities (Peter, 2020). E-banking plays vital role in current scenario (Singh and Mahajan, 2021). E-banking enables customers to obtain information about financial services (Kumari and Chatteraj, 2020).

III. METHODOLOGY AND DATA ANALYSIS

The study is based on primary data and secondary data. Primary data has been collected from the state of West Bengal. The sample size of the study is 200. 64% of the respondents are male and 36% of the respondents are female. The respondents includes urban customers and rural customers of banks. The respondents are customers of private sector banks and public sector banks. 72% of the respondents agree that private sector banks deliver better service than public sector banks. 82% of the respondents agree that the cost of public sector banks is less than private sector banks. 79% of the respondents agree that many customers avoid online banking due to security threat. 68% of the respondents agree that rural masses are not interested in availing banking facilities due to bank charges. 77% of the respondents agree that the number of bank branches should be increased in rural areas. 94% of the respondents agree that urban customers avail online banking more than rural customers. 63% of the respondents agree that employees of private sector banks are more efficient than public sector banks. 55% of the respondents agree that urban customers prefer private sector banks more than public sector banks.

IV. CONCLUSION

Private sector banks adopt advanced technology to provide high quality banking services to customers. Rural masses suffer to avail banking services due to inadequate number of bank branches in villages. Customer satisfaction is the major factor behind customer loyalty. Bank employees are not able to communicate properly to the rural customers. The online banking services of private sector banks is better than public sector banks. Urban customers avail banking services more than rural customers. Banks emphasize on customer satisfaction to enhance customer loyalty. Banks should provide credit facilities to rural people on easy terms. Both urban and rural customers face difficulties due to security threat. Customer satisfaction is the key factor behind customer retention in banking sector.

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